

Pandemic Software Development: The Student Experiences from Developing a COVID-19 Information Dashboard

General Information: We are conducting a study to understand and characterise the challenges, behavioural patterns, practices, and experiences of volunteering students working on a COVID-19 software project during the pandemic. As part of the study, this survey is purposed to understand your experience and challenges faced when working on the project. This survey is voluntary and will take approximately 25 minutes. All information will be kept confidential.

[Demographic]

1. Age: _____
2. Gender: Female / Male / Prefer not to say
3. What is your current level of education? Please select one
 - I am currently doing an undergraduate degree
 - I am currently doing a postgraduate degree
 - Others (Please specify)
4. Please specify your area of study (e.g. Bachelor of Information Technology):
Free text
5. Which of the following best describes your role in this project?
 - Owner
 - Architect
 - Designer
 - Developer
 - Documentation contributor
 - Marketing
 - Information contributor
 - Project manager
 - Tester
 - Others (Please specify):
6. Which area did you work in for this project? Select one or more
 - Data collection (Information collection, news)
 - Data visualization
 - Data updates
 - Promotion
 - Frond-end development
 - Back-end development
 - Translation

- UI/UX
- Others (Please specify):

7. How many years (if any) have you been professionally involved in software development in the industry (except the COVID-19 project)?

- 0
- 1 - 2
- 3 - 5
- 6 -10
- More than 10

[Motivations]

8. Which of the following factors did motivate you to participate in this project? Select one or more

- Learn new skills and technologies
- Learn how a real software system is developed in industry
- Play a positive role in this crisis
- Demonstrate my skills and expertise
- Challenge myself to do technically challenging tasks
- Gain experience and put it in my CV
- Build a network by meeting and communicating with new people
- Experience participating in a student initiated/led project
- Experience working on a crisis related software project
- To occupy free time
- Interested in learning more about the COVID-19 situation
- Others [Please specify]

[General Challenges]

9. The following statements are some challenges you may or may not have faced while working on the COVID-19 project. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements.

Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not Applicable
It was difficult for me to balance my university commitments and working on this project							
It was difficult for me to work on this project from home							

It was difficult to manage my mental health while working on this project from home							
It was difficult to manage my physical health while working on this project							
It was difficult for me to keep my attention away from distractions while working from home							
It was difficult to establish a work-life balance while working from home							
It was difficult to set up my own productive workspace while working from home							
It was difficult for me to stay motivated while working from home							
It was difficult for me to collaborate with the team through a purely online medium							
It was difficult for me to work in a purely online medium							

10. Did you face any other general challenges that have not been previously mentioned while working on the COVID-19 project? Please describe these challenges, if any.

[Data Collection Challenges]

11. The following statements are some data collection challenges you may or may not have faced while working on the COVID-19 project. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements.

Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Somewhat disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not Applicable
It was difficult to find reliable and accurate data							
It was difficult to find data that was up to date							
It was difficult to find data that was consistent across multiple sources							

It was difficult to interpret the data on sources we found							
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12. Did you face any other challenges while collecting data that have not been previously mentioned while working on the COVID-19 project? Please describe these challenges, if any.

[General Strategies/Techniques/Practices]

13. The following statements are some strategies or methods that may or may not have helped you overcome challenges faced while working on the COVID-19 project. Please indicate how frequently each of the strategies were applied.

Statements	Very Often	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
To manage my workload, I worked on tasks with the rest of the team					
To manage my commitments to this project, I worked on it according to a fixed schedule					
To communicate more clearly, I used clear language in messages.					
To communicate more clearly, I used voice calls rather than text messages for discussions					
To collaborate more effectively, I actively responded to teammates' messages					
To boost team morale, I encouraged and acknowledged the efforts of other teammates					
To boost team morale, I celebrated project milestones with the team					
To manage my wellbeing, I regularly distanced myself from the constant feed of news related to COVID-19					
To create visualisations, I looked at how other COVID-19 projects visualized their data					
To keep a healthy work-life balance, I set up a productive workspace separate from my personal space					

14. Did you use any other general strategies that have not been previously mentioned while working on the COVID-19 project? Please describe these strategies, if any, and how effective they were.

[Data Collection Strategies/Techniques/Practices]

21. Please rate your skills in the following soft skills **after** working on the COVID-19 project:

Statements	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Not Applicable
Leadership skills												
Stress management under stressful conditions												
Time management under stressful conditions												
Working online												
Task ownership												
Task prioritisation												
Teamwork												
Understanding of COVID-19												

22. Did you learn or improve on any other non-technical skills that have not been previously mentioned while working on the COVID-19 project? Please describe these skills, if any.

Follow-up [Optional]

[Optional] As a small thank, each participant will receive a Coles gift card (value: 80 AUD). Please leave your email if you would like to receive a Coles gift card (value: 80 AUD).

[Optional] Please leave your contact details here if you have indicated your interest in the previous question

[Optional] Please leave any further comments in the space below